

Supplementary material – data extraction form

This data extraction form is developed from Cochrane’s “Data collection form for intervention reviews: RCTs and non-RCTs” (1)

General Information

Date form completed (<i>dd/mm/yyyy</i>)		30-09-2022	
Name/ID of person extracting data		MDL	
Author(s)		Uhrbrand et al.	
Country of origin		Denmark	
Publication year		2021	
Title of article		Shared decision-making approach to taper postoperative opioids in spine surgery patients with preoperative opioid use: a randomized controlled trial	
Title of journal		Pain	
Volume	Issue	Pages 1-8	
Publication type (<i>e.g. full report, abstract, letter</i>)		Research paper	

Study eligibility

Study Characteristics	Eligibility criteria <i>There are no restrictions on the types of study.</i>				Location in text or source (<i>pg & ¶/fig/table/other</i>)
		Yes	No	Unclear	
Type of study	Randomised Controlled Trial	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Title, abstract, p. 2
	Quasi-randomised Controlled Trial	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Controlled Before and After Study	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Other design (specify):	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Participants	Adult patients scheduled to undergo cervical or lumbar spine surgery due to degenerative conditions	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	p. 2
Types of intervention	Opioid tapering plan and telephone counselling after spine surgery	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	p. 2
Types of comparison	Postoperative standard of care, ie, no opioid tapering plan or telephone counselling	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	p. 2
Types of outcome		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	

measures					
INCLUDE <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		EXCLUDE <input type="checkbox"/>			

Characteristics of included studies

Methods

	Descriptions as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Aim of study (e.g. efficacy, equivalence, pragmatic)	To identify methods that can facilitate opioid tapering after surgery in patients with preoperative opioid use, we conducted a prospective randomized controlled trial (RCT). We hypothesized that the combination of a personalized tapering plan and telephone counselling would reduce postoperative opioid use, reduce contacts with the healthcare system after discharge, increase patient satisfaction, and reduce symptoms possibly related to withdrawal, compared with standard of care.	p. 1
Design (e.g. parallel, crossover, non-RCT)	RCT	Title, abstract, p. 2
Start date	October 22, 2019	p. 2
End date	September 8, 2020	p. 2
Ethical approval needed/ obtained for study	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Unclear The study protocol was approved by the Danish Protection Agency (ID 1-16-02-211-19) and the Central Denmark Region Committees on Health Research Ethics (ID 1-10-72-138-19).	p. 2

Participants

	Description <i>Include comparative information for each intervention or comparison group if available</i>	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Setting (including location and social context)	The Department of Neurosurgery, Aarhus University Hospital, Denmark.	p. 2
Inclusion criteria	To be included in the trial, patients were required to consume opioids daily at least 14 days leading up to surgery. Patients could only be included once during the study period. Patients were included by the primary investigator (P.U.) on the first day after surgery.	p. 2
Exclusion criteria	Patients were excluded if they had severe physical comorbidity (eg, active cancer) or were unable to participate (dementia, language problems, or severe mental illness)	p. 2

Informed consent obtained	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Unclear	Before inclusion and randomization by the primary investigator, signed informed consent was obtained after the provision of oral and written information about the study.	p. 2
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Intervention group

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Group name	Opioid tapering plan and telephone counselling	p. 2
No. randomised to group (specify whether no. people or clusters)	N=55 (M:24, F:31) Mean age = 58.0	p. 5 (table 1) p. 5 (table 1)
Description (include sufficient detail for replication, e.g. content, dose, components)	The personalized opioid tapering plan was made on the day of discharge and as a shared decision-making process between the primary investigator and the patient. The primary investigator called patients 5 to 7 days after discharge and provided guidance and/or adjustments to the tapering plan according to the individual patient's needs.	p. 2

Control group

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Group name	Postoperative standard of care	p. 2
No. randomised to group (specify whether no. people or clusters)	N=55 (M:31, F:24) Mean age = 55.3	p. 5 (table 1) p. 5 (table 1)
Description (include sufficient detail for replication, e.g. content, dose, components)	The control group was treated per standard of care and received no written tapering plan or telephone counselling. The usual procedure in the department was to instruct patients to use immediate-release opioids as needed for their postoperative pain, and coordinate further care and required opioid dose changes with their primary care physician.	p. 2

Outcomes

Outcome 1 – primary outcome

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Outcome name	The number of patients exceeding their daily preoperative opioid consumption by any amount.	p. 3
Outcome definition (<i>with diagnostic criteria if relevant</i>)	Were unable to taper, 1 month after discharge (yes/no). Web-based questionnaire (REDCap) or telephone call and manual data recording.	p. 3

Outcome 2

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Outcome name	The number of patients who succeeded in tapering opioids to zero at 3 months after discharge	p. 3
Outcome definition (<i>with diagnostic criteria if relevant</i>)	Yes/no dichotomous outcome. Web-based questionnaire (REDCap) or telephone call and manual data recording	p. 3

Outcome 3

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Outcome name	Pain-related contacts to the primary and/or secondary health care system during the first 2 weeks after discharge.	p. 3
Outcome definition (<i>with diagnostic criteria if relevant</i>)	Yes/no dichotomous outcome. Web-based questionnaire (REDCap) or telephone call and manual data recording.	p. 3

Outcome 4

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Outcome name	Patient satisfaction with pain treatment over the first 2 weeks after discharge.	p. 3

Outcome definition (<i>with diagnostic criteria if relevant</i>)	Ordinal scale with 5 options converted to dichotomous outcome, yes [very satisfied, satisfied], no [neither satisfied nor dissatisfied, dissatisfied, very dissatisfied]. Web-based questionnaire (REDCap) or telephone call and manual data recording.	p. 3
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Outcome 5

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (<i>pg & ¶/fig/table/other</i>)
Outcome name	The presence of any symptoms possibly related to withdrawal during opioid tapering in the first month after discharge.	p. 3
Outcome definition (<i>with diagnostic criteria if relevant</i>)	Yes/no Web-based questionnaire (REDCap) or telephone call and manual data recording	p. 3

Pain was measured by NRS – showed no statistically significant difference between the intervention group and the control group. p. 6 Figure 2.

Follow up

Follow up	3 months	p. 3
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Conclusion

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Conclusion	<p>Overall, 110 patients were randomized; 55 into the intervention and control groups each. Five patients (proportion 5 0.09, 95% confidence interval [CI] [0.04-0.21]) in the intervention group compared with 13 patients (0.25, 95% CI [0.15-0.39]) in the control group were unable to taper opioids to their preoperative consumption 1 month after discharge (P 5 0.03) (primary outcome). Likewise, more patients in the intervention group succeeded in tapering opioids to zero 3 months after discharge (37 patients; 0.71, 95% CI [0.57-0.82] vs 23 patients; 0.43, 95% CI [0.30-0.56], P 5 0.003). Fewer patients in the intervention group had pain-related contacts to health care the first 2 weeks after discharge (21 patients; 0.40, 95% CI [0.28-0.54] vs 31 patients; 0.60, 95% CI [0.46-0.73], P 5 0.04). There was no difference in satisfaction with pain treatment over the first 2 weeks or the incidence of withdrawal symptoms during the first month after discharge. Pain intensity was similar between both groups at all time points. These results suggest that a personalized tapering plan at discharge combined with telephone counselling 1 week after discharge assists patients in postoperative opioid tapering.</p> <p>Conclusion: Opioid tapering after discharge poses a significant clinical concern for patients with preoperative use of opioids. A personalized tapering plan at discharge and telephone counselling 1 week after discharge may assist such patients with postoperative opioid tapering. We believe that our study provides valuable information on how to use shared decision making to taper opioids after surgery in patients with preoperative opioid use.</p>	<p>Abstract</p> <p>p. 7</p>

References

1. Cochrane. Data collection form for intervention reviews for RCTs and non-RCTs - template [Internet]. The Cochrane Collaboration. 2022 [cited 2022 Sep 15]. Available from: <https://dplp.cochrane.org/data-extraction-forms>